

Supplemental material

Title: Germplasm diversity of sunflower volatile terpenoid profiles across vegetative and reproductive organs

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Number of pages: 11

Number of figures: 3

Number of tables: 14

Table S1. The 12 cultivated sunflower genotypes (inbred lines) for which volatile phytochemistry was assessed in this study. All inbred lines were obtained from the USDA National Plant Germplasm System. The North Central Regional Plant Introduction Station (NCRPIS, Ames, IA) accession number is listed, along with the USDA Plant Introduction number for the USDA germplasm accession or French INRA (Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique) accession from which the inbred line was derived through single-seed descent. These “Core 12” lines represent approximately half of the allelic diversity present in the Sunflower Association Mapping (SAM) panel of 288 accessions (Mandel et al., 2011). Breeding pool refers to membership in either the maintainer (HA) or restorer (RHA) breeding pools, or open-pollinated varieties (OPV). Market class refers to Oil and NonOil varieties within the HA and RHA breeding pools, a distinction that does not apply clearly to OPV varieties nor line 262 from INRA.

Line (full name)	Line (short name)	Breeding pool/ market class	USDA NCRPIS accession	Derived from USDA or INRA accession	Original source
UGA-SAM1-020	SAM 020	HA-Oil	Ames 31713	PI 597368	USDA-developed
UGA-SAM1-022	SAM 022	RHA-Oil	Ames 31715	PI 597373	USDA-developed
UGA-SAM1-027	SAM 027	HA-NonOil	Ames 31720	PI 599783	USDA-developed
UGA-SAM1-093	SAM 093	OPV	Ames 31785	PI 386230	Khazakhstan
UGA-SAM1-094	SAM 094	OPV	Ames 31786	PI 476853	Burpee (Mammoth)
UGA-SAM1-176	SAM 176	HA-Oil	Ames 31868	PI 599778	USDA-developed
UGA-SAM1-185	SAM 185	HA-Oil	Ames 31877	PI 599984	USDA-developed
UGA-SAM1-191	SAM 191	RHA-Oil	Ames 31883	PI 603989	USDA-developed
UGA-SAM1-203	SAM 203	RHA-Oil	Ames 31895	PI 617099	USDA-developed
UGA-SAM1-237	SAM 237	RHA-NonOil	Ames 31929	PI 664202	USDA-developed
UGA-SAM1-240	SAM 240	HA-NonOil	Ames 31932	PI 664225	USDA-developed
UGA-SAM1-262	SAM 262	HA-INRA	Ames 31954	SF 230	INRA (France)

Table S2. Total number of volatile compounds detected and identified via SPME-GC-MS in each genotype (pooling all four organ types assessed), as well as the proportional breakdown of compounds classified as terpenoids (divided into monoterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, and diterpenoids), fatty acid derivatives, and other compounds. Percentages may not sum to exactly 100% due to rounding.

Core 12 genotype	Number of compounds	% terpenoids	% monoterpenoids	% sesquiterpenoids	% diterpenoids	% fatty acid derivatives	% other compounds
SAM 020	82	82.9	34.1	47.6	1.2	0	17.0
SAM 022	90	80.0	38.8	40.0	1.1	1.1	18.9
SAM 027	107	74.8	37.5	36.4	0.9	3.7	21.5
SAM 093	102	78.4	46.0	30.4	2.0	0	21.6
SAM 094	95	80.0	44.2	34.8	1.0	0	20.0
SAM 176	72	80.5	37.5	40.3	2.7	0	19.4
SAM 185	84	85.7	40.5	44.0	1.2	0	14.2
SAM 191	85	88.2	41.1	45.8	1.2	0	11.7
SAM 203	82	79.3	37.8	40.2	1.2	0	20.7
SAM 237	82	81.7	37.8	42.7	1.2	1.2	17.1
SAM 240	93	83.8	39.8	43.0	1.0	0	16.2
SAM 262	71	77.5	42.2	33.9	1.4	1.4	21.1

Table S3. Volatile profiles as assessed by SPME-GC-MS in the four organ types assessed (averaged across the twelve plant genotypes). The average number of compounds detected and total volatile abundance (mass-normalized peak area) are reported, along with the proportional breakdown of mass-normalized peak area by compound class: terpenoids (divided into monoterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, and diterpenoids), and other compounds. Values represent mean \pm SE for each metric reported, calculated across all replicate samples. Percentages may not sum to exactly 100% due to rounding.

Organ	Number of compounds	Total volatile abundance	% terpenoids	% monoterpenoids	% sesquiterpenoids	% diterpenoids	% fatty acid derivatives	% other compounds
Petals	16.8 \pm 0.6	33064 \pm 2517	98.1 \pm 0.3	94.5 \pm 0.6	3.6 \pm 0.5	0	0.03 \pm 0.02	1.9 \pm 0.3
Disc florets	24.3 \pm 0.8	50409 \pm 3589	96.8 \pm 0.5	90.3 \pm 1.0	6.5 \pm 0.8	0.01 \pm 0.00	0.01 \pm 0.01	3.2 \pm 0.5
Bracts	23.4 \pm 1.3	28401 \pm 3177	96.1 \pm 0.6	80.5 \pm 1.9	15.5 \pm 1.6	0.06 \pm 0.03	0	3.9 \pm 0.6
Leaves	29.2 \pm 1.7	23495 \pm 2983	93.2 \pm 0.9	54.5 \pm 2.7	38.2 \pm 2.8	0.50 \pm 0.07	0.02 \pm 0.02	6.8 \pm 0.9

Table S4. Volatile profiles as assessed by SPME-GC-MS in the twelve plant genotypes assessed (averaged across the four organ types). The average number of compounds detected and total volatile abundance (mass-normalized peak area) are reported, along with the proportional breakdown of mass-normalized peak area by compound class: terpenoids (divided into monoterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, and diterpenoids), and other compounds. Values represent mean \pm SE for each metric reported, calculated across all replicate samples. Percentages may not sum to exactly 100% due to rounding.

Core 12 genotype	Number of compounds	Total volatile abundance	% terpenoids	% monoterpenoids	% sesquiterpenoids	% diterpenoids	% fatty acid derivatives	% other compounds
SAM 020	24.1 \pm 1.6	30864 \pm 4165	94.8 \pm 1.9	69.4 \pm 5.0	25.2 \pm 4.2	0.20 \pm 0.08	0	5.2 \pm 1.9
SAM 022	22.8 \pm 1.3	33341 \pm 6724	94.8 \pm 1.3	74.0 \pm 4.1	20.5 \pm 3.7	0.24 \pm 0.10	0.03 \pm 0.03	5.1 \pm 1.3
SAM 027	23.0 \pm 1.3	32098 \pm 2819	95.8 \pm 2.4	80.7 \pm 2.4	15.1 \pm 2.3	0.07 \pm 0.03	0.04 \pm 0.04	4.0 \pm 0.6
SAM 093	20.2 \pm 1.3	23108 \pm 3258	94.3 \pm 1.5	81.0 \pm 3.4	13.1 \pm 2.5	0.18 \pm 0.10	0	5.6 \pm 1.5
SAM 094	25.1 \pm 1.7	35821 \pm 4445	96.2 \pm 1.0	79.6 \pm 3.6	16.5 \pm 3.4	0.01 \pm 0.01	0	3.8 \pm 1.0
SAM 176	20.2 \pm 1.2	28694 \pm 3731	96.7 \pm 0.7	82.4 \pm 3.3	14.0 \pm 2.7	0.21 \pm 0.09	0	3.2 \pm 0.7
SAM 185	24.0 \pm 1.7	25324 \pm 2146	95.6 \pm 1.4	76.8 \pm 4.2	18.6 \pm 3.9	0.11 \pm 0.06	0	4.3 \pm 1.4
SAM 191	25.9 \pm 1.7	31366 \pm 3422	95.7 \pm 0.8	68.1 \pm 5.9	27.3 \pm 5.3	0.19 \pm 0.09	0	4.2 \pm 0.8
SAM 203	20.6 \pm 1.1	35429 \pm 4894	95.9 \pm 0.8	86.4 \pm 3.0	9.2 \pm 2.3	0.28 \pm 0.10	0	4.0 \pm 0.8
SAM 237	25.6 \pm 2.6	25926 \pm 2156	96.0 \pm 0.7	74.7 \pm 5.6	21.1 \pm 5.3	0.09 \pm 0.05	0.04 \pm 0.04	3.9 \pm 0.7
SAM 240	30.4 \pm 2.1	52673 \pm 4491	97.9 \pm 0.2	79.1 \pm 4.1	18.8 \pm 3.9	0.02 \pm 0.02	0	2.0 \pm 1.1
SAM 262	24.2 \pm 2.5	34318 \pm 6058	94.6 \pm 1.8	82.3 \pm 4.2	12.1 \pm 2.9	0.19 \pm 0.08	0.08 \pm 0.08	5.2 \pm 1.9

Table S5. Fold-change variation in volatile compound profile metrics across the Core 12 genotypes and four organ types (48 genotype-by-organ combination means).

Number of compounds	Total volatile abundance	% terpenoids	% monoterpenoids	% sesquiterpenoids	% diterpenoids	% fatty acid derivatives	% other compounds
3.21	9.34	1.14	2.57	110.8	26.7	20	21.5

Table S6. Fold-change variation in volatile compound profile metrics across the Core 12 genotypes within the four organ types. A cell with (-) indicates that $n \leq 1$ genotype within the organ type contained a non-zero value for the metric.

Organ	Number of compounds	Total volatile abundance	% terpenoids	% monoterpenoids	% sesquiterpenoids	% diterpenoids	% fatty acid derivatives	% other compounds
Petal	1.62	2.28	1.03	1.08	11.60	-	1.00	6.00
Disk Floret	1.49	2.35	1.05	1.10	4.34	1.33	10.00	5.15
Bract	2.19	3.74	1.07	1.27	4.28	4.28	-	5.78
Leaf	2.08	5.98	1.11	1.80	2.52	16.00	0.20	4.77

Table S7. Fold-change variation in volatile compound profile metrics across the four organs within each Core 12 genotype. A cell with (-) indicates that $n \leq 1$ tissue type within the line contained a non-zero value for the metric.

Genotype	Number of compounds	Total volatile abundance	% terpenoids	% monoterpenoids	% sesquiterpenoids	% diterpenoids	% fatty acid derivatives	% other compounds
SAM 020	1.67	2.84	1.11	2.36	14.20	5.00	-	17.5
SAM 022	1.38	3.34	1.06	1.72	16.40	7.14	-	3.47
SAM 027	1.53	1.91	1.03	1.57	6.39	-	10	2.33
SAM 093	1.53	5.55	1.12	1.66	6.20	20.00	-	5.60
SAM 094	2.00	2.29	1.06	1.62	14.18	-	-	4.26
SAM 176	2.01	3.20	1.05	1.57	13.78	17.50	-	7.25
SAM 185	1.77	1.49	1.05	1.79	8.72	-	-	4.18
SAM 191	1.73	2.40	1.06	2.49	14.57	-	-	6.70
SAM 203	1.54	2.64	1.07	1.56	56.80	2.66	-	5.78
SAM 237	2.69	1.71	1.04	2.10	9.82	-	-	8.50
SAM 240	2.06	1.57	1.01	1.59	10.29	-	-	1.92
SAM 262	2.16	4.59	1.07	1.37	9.12	1.50	-	3.90

Table S8. The four most abundant compounds identified by SPME-GC-MS as a percentage of the overall volatile profile across the Core 12 genotypes and four organ types (48 genotype-by-organ combination means).

Core 12 genotype	Organ	Major compounds (% of all volatiles)			
		L-Alpha-Pinene	Sabinene	Gamma-Terpinene	O-Cymene
SAM 020	Petal	44.7	26.0	6.2	2.2
SAM 022	Petal	36.3	27.4	6.0	2.5
SAM 027	Petal	40.1	28.0	5.6	2.1
SAM 093	Petal	53.7	18.8	4.6	2.4
SAM 094	Petal	37.7	31.0	6.6	2.3
SAM 176	Petal	77.2	10.9	2.5	1.0
SAM 185	Petal	52.2	23.8	4.5	1.9
SAM 191	Petal	53.4	23.8	4.9	2.4
SAM 203	Petal	57.7	11.3	4.1	2.3
SAM 237	Petal	33.2	29.6	8.1	3.7
SAM 240	Petal	51.9	21.8	5.4	1.7
SAM 262	Petal	59.5	19.3	3.0	1.5
SAM 020	Disc Floret	43.9	22.7	5.9	1.9
SAM 022	Disc Floret	51.7	12.2	3.2	1.3
SAM 027	Disc Floret	48.0	15.3	4.6	1.4
SAM 093	Disc Floret	54.3	15.1	3.7	1.3
SAM 094	Disc Floret	41.6	23.4	7.3	2.1
SAM 176	Disc Floret	62.1	13.8	3.7	1.3
SAM 185	Disc Floret	55.4	15.2	3.3	1.5
SAM 191	Disc Floret	62.2	10.7	3.1	1.3
SAM 203	Disc Floret	60.6	9.0	2.6	1.5
SAM 237	Disc Floret	34.7	24.1	5.9	2.1
SAM 240	Disc Floret	57.0	13.8	4.1	1.2
SAM 262	Disc Floret	59.9	19.2	3.0	0.7
SAM 020	Bract	50.9	10.4	1.4	0.4
SAM 022	Bract	55.4	9.9	1.2	0.4
SAM 027	Bract	51.1	7.9	1.5	0.8
SAM 093	Bract	49.7	8.8	1.1	0.6
SAM 094	Bract	39.5	12.4	1.7	0.4
SAM 176	Bract	63.8	7.4	0.7	0.6
SAM 185	Bract	44.9	8.7	1.3	0.6
SAM 191	Bract	55.9	4.0	0.4	0.8
SAM 203	Bract	54.6	7.8	1.2	1.1
SAM 237	Bract	44.6	9.3	0.7	0.3
SAM 240	Bract	47.9	9.5	1.7	0.8
SAM 262	Bract	63.1	8.7	1.5	0.3
SAM 020	Leaf	6.3	9.1	1.5	0.6
SAM 022	Leaf	8.2	9.9	2.4	0.5
SAM 027	Leaf	6.6	11.4	2.5	0.4
SAM 093	Leaf	10.2	12.9	2.6	0.5
SAM 094	Leaf	8.2	13.6	4	1.5
SAM 176	Leaf	12.5	11.4	2.8	0.7
SAM 185	Leaf	11.7	13.7	2.9	0.5
SAM 191	Leaf	6.5	6.0	2.1	0.9
SAM 203	Leaf	10.8	8.3	2.4	0.8
SAM 237	Leaf	7.1	8.4	2.3	0.7
SAM 240	Leaf	9.3	7.0	3	0.9
SAM 262	Leaf	13.7	14.5	3.7	1.1
Average %		40.9	14.5	3.3	1.3

Table S9. The most abundant compounds identified by SPME-GC-MS as a percentage of the overall volatile profile in each of the Core 12 genotypes across the four organ types (mean of replicate samples) and grand mean across organs.

SAM 020	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	36.7	6.3	50.8	45.1	44.7
Sabinene	17.0	9.1	10.4	22.5	25.9
D.Limonene	8.3	20.8	3.7	6.0	2.6
Beta.Gurjunene	6.0	6.6	10.7	4.4	2.3
Beta.Cubebene	5.0	15.4	2.9	1.6	0.1
Gamma.Terpinene	3.7	1.5	1.4	5.6	6.2
Oxime.methoxy.phenyl	2.9	8.0	2.2	0.7	0.7
Alpha.Terpinene	1.8	0.6	0.5	2.7	3.2
O.Cymene	1.1	0.6	0.3	1.5	2.2

SAM 022	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	37.9	8.2	55.4	51.7	36.3
Sabinene	14.9	9.9	9.9	12.2	27.4
D.Limonene	11.4	29.5	5.7	6.0	4.2
Beta.Gurjunene	5.0	3.0	8.9	6.2	1.8
Gamma.Terpinene	3.2	2.4	1.2	3.2	6.0
Oxime.methoxy.phenyl	2.8	5.9	1.4	1.9	1.9
Bornyl acetate	1.5	0.1	1.8	3.7	0.4
Alpha.Terpinene	1.4	0.5	0.4	1.7	3.2
O.Cymene	1.2	0.5	0.4	1.3	2.5

SAM 027	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	36.4	6.5	51.1	48.0	40.0
Sabinene	15.6	11.4	7.9	15.3	27.9
D.Limonene	9.5	23.1	5.4	7.2	2.4
Beta.Gurjunene	6.9	6.2	11.6	4.7	5.2
Gamma.Terpinene	3.5	2.5	1.5	4.6	5.6
Beta.Cubebene	3.3	12.2	0.6	0.6	0.1
Bornyl acetate	2.9	5.6	3.4	1.9	0.6
Oxime.methoxy.phenyl	1.9	3.1	1.0	1.9	1.3
Alpha.Terpinene	1.6	0.4	0.6	2.1	3.0
O.Cymene	1.2	0.4	0.8	1.4	2.1

SAM 093	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	42.0	10.1	49.7	54.3	53.7
Sabinene	13.9	12.9	8.8	15.1	18.8
D.Limonene	8.9	23.8	4.0	6.2	1.5
Beta.Gurjunene	5.2	6.6	7.1	2.7	4.6
Oxime.methoxy.phenyl	3.7	8.7	2.8	1.4	1.9
Gamma.Terpinene	3.0	2.6	1.1	3.7	4.6
Beta.Cubebene	2.4	8.2	0.4	0.8	0.3
Bornyl acetate	2.3	1.9	6.7	0.6	0.1
O.Cymene	1.2	0.5	0.6	1.3	2.4
Alpha.Terpinene	1.0	0.7	0.4	1.8	1.3

SAM 094	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	31.5	8.1	39.5	40.6	37.7
Sabinene	20.6	13.6	12.4	24.9	31.3
Beta.Gurjunene	5.3	4.9	10.5	3.2	2.6
Gamma.Terpinene	4.9	4.0	1.6	7.4	6.6
Alpha.Terpinene	2.2	1.4	0.6	3.8	3.2
Bornyl acetate	2.0	0.8	4.9	2.1	0.3

SAM 176	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	53.9	12.4	63.8	62.1	77.2
D.Limonene	11.1	32.5	4.9	5.7	1.2
Sabinene	10.9	11.4	7.3	13.8	10.9
Beta.Cubebene	3.5	10.5	2.3	1.2	0.1
Beta.Gurjunene	2.7	3.7	4.0	1.3	1.6
Gamma.Terpinene	2.4	2.8	0.7	3.7	2.5
Oxime.methoxy.phenyl	1.5	2.6	2.1	0.4	0.8

SAM 185	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	41.0	11.7	44.8	55.3	52.2
Sabinene	15.4	13.7	8.7	15.2	23.8
Beta.Gurjunene	6.0	6.0	11.4	3.2	3.6
D.Limonene	5.9	19.1	1.9	2.4	0.4
Gamma.Terpinene	3.0	2.9	1.3	3.3	4.5
Oxime.methoxy.phenyl	2.2	3.3	0.8	2.7	1.7
Bornyl acetate	2.1	0.3	6.6	1.2	0.4
Alpha.Terpinene	1.3	0.9	0.5	1.5	2.4
O.Cymene	1.1	0.5	0.6	1.5	1.9

SAM 191	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	44.5	6.5	55.9	62.2	53.4
Sabinene	11.1	6.0	4.0	10.7	23.8
D.Limonene	7.2	19.2	4.3	4.6	0.7
Beta.Cubebene	7.1	22.5	3.1	2.2	0.5
Beta.Gurjunene	4.6	4.7	10.1	2.3	1.5
Gamma.Terpinene	2.6	2.0	0.4	3.1	4.9
Caryophyllene	1.4	4.4	0.4	0.8	0.1
Oxime.methoxy.phenyl	1.3	3.1	0.7	0.7	0.9
O.Cymene	1.3	0.9	0.8	1.3	2.4

SAM 203	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	45.9	10.8	54.6	60.6	57.7
D.Limonene	11.4	23.8	6.9	6.6	8.1
Sabinene	9.0	8.3	7.8	9.0	11.2
L.beta.Pinene	5.3	1.4	7.0	6.0	6.9
Beta.Cubebene	3.8	13.4	1.3	0.5	0.1
Gamma.Terpinene	2.6	2.4	1.1	2.6	4.1
Bornyl acetate	2.4	0.5	5.3	2.7	1.0
Oxime.methoxy.phenyl	2.3	5.4	2.3	0.7	0.9
O.Cymene	1.4	0.8	1.1	1.5	2.3

SAM 237	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	29.9	7.0	44.6	34.7	33.2
Sabinene	17.8	8.4	9.3	24.1	29.5
Beta.Gurjunene	7.2	8.8	9.9	5.2	4.8
Gamma.Terpinene	4.2	2.3	0.7	5.9	8.0
Alpha.Terpinene	2.2	0.9	0.4	3.4	4.1
O.Cymene	1.7	0.7	0.3	2.0	3.7
Bornyl acetate	1.5	1.4	3.5	0.6	0.3

SAM 240	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	41.5	9.3	47.9	57.0	51.9
Sabinene	13.0	7.0	9.5	13.8	21.8
D.Limonene	8.5	23.7	4.1	4.7	1.4
Beta.Cubebene	4.8	15.9	2.5	0.5	0.1
Gamma.Terpinene	3.5	3.0	1.7	4.0	5.4
Beta.Gurjunene	3.0	2.0	6.0	2.7	1.5
Bornyl acetate	2.4	0.6	6.6	1.9	0.7
Alpha.Terpinene	1.4	0.7	0.5	1.8	2.7
Terpinen.4.ol	1.3	0.1	0.7	1.6	2.7
O.Cymene	1.1	0.9	0.8	1.2	1.7

SAM 262	Mean %	Leaf	Bract	Disk	Petal
L.alpha.Pinene	49.0	13.7	63.0	59.9	59.5
Sabinene	15.4	14.5	8.7	19.2	19.3
D.Limonene	9.8	27.1	5.1	4.2	2.8
Beta.Gurjunene	3.0	2.6	5.8	1.6	1.9
Beta.Cubebene	2.9	9.0	1.5	0.8	0.3
Gamma.Terpinene	2.8	3.6	1.5	3.0	3.0
Bornyl acetate	1.4	1.6	3.1	0.6	0.2
Terpinen.4.ol	1.3	0.1	0.1	2.2	2.9
Alpha.Terpinene	1.3	1.4	0.5	1.5	1.7

Table S10. Total number of volatile compounds detected and identified via SPME-GC-MS in *Helianthus* petals in recent studies, as well as the proportional breakdown of compounds classified as terpenoids (divided into monoterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, and diterpenoids), fatty acid derivatives, and other compounds. Percentages may not sum to exactly 100% due to rounding.

Study	Species	Number of compounds	% terpenoids	% monoterpenoids	% sesquiterpenoids	% diterpenoids	% fatty acid derivatives	% other compounds
Current study	Cultivated <i>H. annuus</i> (12 lines)	83	73.5	49.4	24.1	0	4.8	21.6
Bahmani et al. (2022)	Wild <i>H. annuus</i> (1 population)	79	83.5	30.4	44.3	8.8	1.3	15.2
Bahmani et al. (2022)	Wild <i>Helianthus</i> genus (24 species)	210	70.0	23.3	42.8	3.8	1.9	28.1

Table S11. Total number of volatile compounds detected and identified via SPME-GC-MS in *Helianthus* leaves in recent studies, as well as the proportional breakdown of compounds classified as terpenoids (divided into monoterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, and diterpenoids), fatty acid derivatives, and other compounds. Percentages may not sum to exactly 100% due to rounding.

Study	Species	Number of compounds	% terpenoids	% monoterpenoids	% sesquiterpenoids	% diterpenoids	% fatty acid derivatives	% other compounds
Current study	Cultivated <i>H. annuus</i> (12 lines)	72	77.7	25.9	50.6	1.2	2.4	19.7
Adams et al. (2017)	Wild <i>H. annuus</i> (20 populations)	83	79.5	39.7	33.8	6.0	1.2	19.3
Bahmani et al. (2022)	Wild <i>H. annuus</i> (1 population)	67	88.1	40.3	38.9	8.9	0	11.9
Bahmani et al. (2022)	Wild <i>Helianthus</i> genus (37 species)	467	62.7	17.8	41.3	3.6	4.0	33.2

Table S12. Volatile profiles as assessed by SPME-GC-MS in leaves and petals of one population of wild *Helianthus annuus* from Konza Prairie, Kansas (KON) by Bahmani et al. (2022). The average number of compounds detected is reported along with the proportional breakdown of mass-normalized peak area by compound class: terpenoids (divided into monoterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, and diterpenoids), and other compounds. Values represent mean \pm SE for each metric reported, calculated across all replicate samples. Entries with values representing between 0-0.1% of volatile profile composition are rounded up to 0.1%, and percentages may not sum to 100% due to rounding.

Organ	Number of compounds	Total volatile abundance	% terpenoids	% monoterpenoids	% sesquiterpenoids	% diterpenoids	% fatty acid derivatives	% other compounds
Petals	48.2 \pm 0.7	207,935 \pm 57562	97.8 \pm 0.4	92.4 \pm 1.1	4.7 \pm 0.9	0.6 \pm 0.1	0	2.1 \pm 0.4
Leaves	60.5 \pm 7.5	157,928 \pm 54931	98.1 \pm 0.5	66 \pm 1.0	30.7 \pm 1.1	1.4 \pm 0.1	0.1 \pm 0.1	1.8 \pm 0.4

Table S13. Volatile profiles as assessed by SPME-GC-MS in leaves of 20 wild populations of *Helianthus annuus* by Adams et al. (2017). The average number of compounds detected is reported along with the proportional breakdown of mass-normalized peak area by compound class: terpenoids (divided into monoterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, and diterpenoids), and other compounds. Values represent mean \pm SE for each metric reported, calculated across all population means reported. Entries with values representing between 0-0.1% of volatile profile composition are rounded up to 0.1%, and percentages may not sum to 100% due to rounding.

Number of compounds	% terpenoids	% monoterpenoids	% sesquiterpenoids	% diterpenoids	% fatty acid derivatives	% other compounds	% not identified
54.2 \pm 2.3	88.4 \pm 1.7	71.9 \pm 4.9	15.4 \pm 4.1	1.1 \pm 0.3	0.1 \pm 0.1	3.8 \pm 0.7	7.77 \pm 1.1

Table S14. Volatile profiles as assessed by SPME-GC-MS in leaves (n=37) and petals (n=24) of 40 species of wild *Helianthus* by Bahmani et al. (2022). The average number of compounds detected is reported along with the proportional breakdown of mass-normalized peak area by compound class: terpenoids (divided into monoterpenoids, sesquiterpenoids, and diterpenoids), and other compounds. Values represent mean \pm SE for each metric reported, calculated across all replicate samples. Percentages may not sum to exactly 100% due to rounding.

Organ	Number of compounds	Total volatile abundance	% terpenoids	% monoterpenoids	% sesquiterpenoids	% diterpenoids	% fatty acid derivatives	% other compounds
Petals	29.2 \pm 15.4	159,990 \pm 194,308	73.9 \pm 30.6	42.8 \pm 26.8	30.9 \pm 23.0	0.2 \pm 0.4	1.4 \pm 3.0	24.6 \pm 28.6
Leaves	52.7 \pm 11.7	354,907 \pm 382,914	93.8 \pm 11.5	39.7 \pm 25.0	53.3 \pm 24.7	0.7 \pm 0.9	0.5 \pm 1.5	5.6 \pm 10.0

Figure S1. Left: negative correlation among the Core 12 genotypes between L-alpha-pinene and sabinene in petals. Right: negative correlation among the Core 12 genotypes between L-alpha-pinene and sabinene in disc florets.

Figure S2. Top Left: positive correlation among the Core 12 genotypes between total monoterpene abundance and total volatile abundance in leaves. Top Right: positive correlation among the Core 12 genotypes between total sesquiterpene abundance and total volatile abundance in leaves. Bottom: positive correlation among the Core 12 genotypes between the total monoterpene abundance and total sesquiterpene abundance in leaves.

Figure S3. Left: positive correlation among the Core 12 genotypes between the proportion of monoterpenoids in bracts and the proportion of monoterpenoids in leaves. Right: positive correlation among the Core 12 genotypes between the proportion of sesquiterpenoids in bracts and the proportion of sesquiterpenoids in leaves.

